

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES IN FINE ARTS LESSONS**Ibadullayeva Shakhnoza Ilkhamovna**

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Abstract: The article talks about the development of students' creative abilities in fine arts lessons, and also talks about the process of organizing activities, highlighting some points.

Keywords: Creative abilities, conditions, education, skills, primary class, art, drawing art, initiative, visual perception, personality.

Every teacher raising a new generation must seriously think about how to develop the creative and artistic abilities inherent in a person, strengthen spiritual strength, and help him find himself. In any profession, in any work, creativity is the basis for moving forward. Art lessons contain enormous creative potential. Classes provide many opportunities for self-expression and development of abilities. In the system of training and education of school students, fine arts lessons are of great importance. In combination with other academic subjects, they have a noticeable developmental effect on the child. This is the ability to perceive, feel, understand the beautiful in life, in art, the desire to create the beautiful oneself, to appreciate the beautiful in surrounding objects. An emotionally positive decision towards creativity contributes to the successful solution of educational tasks in fine arts lessons. In the psychological and pedagogical literature, more and more attention is paid to the search for methods and teaching techniques that contribute to more successful development of artistic abilities and ensure the activation of mental and practical activity of subjects of the educational process. It is necessary to develop creative activity in people from childhood, from school. In this matter, fine art and music provide great assistance - subjects that can use opportunities for the real development of the creative abilities of the child's personality, his creative individuality. In the lessons, it is necessary to teach the student to distinguish between the main types and genres of fine art, to analyze the content and figurative language of works of different types and genres of fine art. When completing assignments, the student must be offered various materials (gouache, watercolor, natural and improvised materials), this promotes a creative approach to the execution of the work. The alternation of activities contributes to the diversified development of the student. Aesthetic education is aimed at developing a sense of beauty, forming high aesthetic tastes, the ability to understand and appreciate works of art, historical and architectural monuments, the beauty and richness of native nature. It is better to use for these purposes the capabilities of each academic subject, especially literature, music, and fine arts, which have great cognitive and educational power.

All this makes us think about how to make the learning process effective in accordance with the requirements of life. In modern schools, numerous innovative technologies are used to solve this problem: Personally-oriented learning, gaming technologies, project method, collaborative learning, individual and differentiated learning, modular learning and others.

The development of creative abilities is the most important task of education. After all, this process awakens initiative, independence in decision-making, the habit of free self-expression, self-confidence, because the true goal of learning is not only the mastery of certain knowledge, skills and abilities, but also the development and education of a creative person.

Creativity is the highest form of activity, independence, the ability to create something new and original. Creativity is needed in any sphere of human activity: scientific, artistic, production and technical, economic, etc.

The development of students' personality in the process of organizing activities highlights the following points:

1. Characteristics of the creative abilities of schoolchildren.

Every child is unique and talented - it is a whole world of unrealized possibilities. The teacher's task is to reveal these talents and create conditions for the child's creative realization. As a child, everyone draws. The child tries to realize what is visible and display it. But not everyone succeeds, because you need to know how to draw, where to start and what to use. Drawing develops spatial thinking, imagination, aesthetic taste, and fosters hard work.

General age-related characteristics manifest themselves differently in each child, depending on his or her individuality.

The most important source of children's imagination is emotions. Children's creativity is always full of bright positive emotions. Thanks to this circumstance, creativity has great attractive power. Creative work is an opportunity to express your delight in the world around you in the language of various materials or to show your rejection of it.

Creative work in a fine arts lesson is a kind of connecting link between a child and an adult. The activity of creative imagination almost never occurs without the help and participation of a teacher; his role is to build an activity together with children so that children can create and realize the ideas of their creative works.

In order to properly guide children's creativity, you need to know the features of children's visual activity. This knowledge will help you find the key to a child's heart, establish contact with him, develop his artistic abilities and aesthetic feelings, will help to understand how the student perceives reality, how his visual perception, imagination, spatial concepts, memory, etc. develop.

It is necessary to do everything possible to preserve the child's craving for visual activity, and if it does not exist, then awaken and then develop cognitive interests. The increased propensity of students for visual activities is an indicator of their awakening abilities for artistic creativity and the development of interest in it. And it is possible to develop interest in creativity in each individual only taking into account individual abilities.

Fine arts classes provide ample opportunities to study the characteristics of children and implement an individual approach to each child, which contributes to the development of not only their artistic and creative abilities, but also attention, observation, perseverance and will. In creative development, the general and the special, the individual, are manifested.

The degree of originality of an artistic image is determined by the vigilance of vision and the sharpness of perception of life, the aesthetic taste and imagination of the artist. It is these qualities that a teacher should cultivate in his student during art lessons. The main objective of fine arts lessons is to develop the artistic and creative abilities of children through targeted and organized learning.

Creative individuality can manifest itself at different levels. From transferring old knowledge, skills, experience to a new situation to the ability to find a new option.

Creative abilities are individual creativity in various areas of human activity. Creative activity is always associated with the creation of something new, the discovery of new knowledge, the discovery of new possibilities in oneself. This in itself becomes a strong and effective incentive for knowledge and effort. Such activities strengthen positive self-esteem, increase the level of aspirations, generate self-confidence and a sense of satisfaction in the successes achieved.

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